

Mental Health and Teachers' Commitment Using an Explanatory Sequential Design

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Abstract. This study aims to determine what quantitative results need further explanation to determine what school program can be initiated to boost teachers' work satisfaction in improving teaching commitment amidst the mental health experience of public school teachers teaching in Matina Central Elementary School, Matina District, Davao City Division. 82 public school teachers were identified as respondents through a simple random sampling technique, and five (5) participants were purposively selected for the in-depth interview. The study utilized a mixed-methods sequential explanatory design. Two data collection methods were used: the quantitative and the qualitative phases. After the quantitative data analysis, the results revealed that the level of teacher commitment in terms of commitment to school, commitment to students, commitment to teaching, and commitment to the profession was moderate, which means that it was sometimes evident. Moreover, based on the result, the level of the mental health of teachers in terms of lifestyle habits, work satisfaction, social relations, and financial struggles was moderate, which means that it was sometimes evident. In addition, the quantitative findings were supported by the qualitative findings. Thus, it was found that the school program that boosts teachers' work satisfaction in improving teaching commitment amidst mental health experience of teachers revealed three major themes: recognizing and rewarding positive working conditions, and increasing opportunities for growth.

KEY WORDS

1. Mental health experience
2. teacher commitment
3. teachers
4. explanatory sequential design
5. Davao City Division

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1. Introduction

A good education is essential to both individual development and the betterment of society. Through education, knowledge is passed on from generation to generation, and teachers keep that flame. Teachers' commitment to their jobs is essential since it affects the caliber of education and pupils' general development. Teacher commitment has been cited as one of the most essential elements in the development

and sustainability of education. A solid and committed workforce is crucial for schools to achieve their educational goals, as every successful institution was built with the help of dedicated and competent teachers.

In Davao City, Cagape et al. (2021) aimed to determine the level of commitment of public secondary school teachers during the pandemic. The research sample consisted of 1,096 public

secondary school teachers. The survey revealed that teachers are, on average, extremely committed. In terms of commitment to the classroom, students, teaching, and the profession, the results also indicated that teachers had high levels of commitment.

The effectiveness of our educational system relies largely on teacher commitment. Addressing the challenges that impede teacher commitment is essential to keep and inspire our educators. The complex connections between teacher commitment and mental health experiences are an interesting topic for investigation, particularly in the Philippines. While the importance of teacher commitment is well acknowledged in educational discourse, the intricate interplay with mental health has received little attention, particularly when considering culturally acceptable frameworks and methods. This study seeks to illuminate these connections, ultimately providing practitioners with the knowledge required to develop a more resilient and committed teaching workforce given the prevalence of mental health difficulties.

The aforementioned statements suggest that significant research is required to delve into the multifaceted nature of teacher commitment and mental health, and to identify the determinants of their development and sustainability. This prompted the researcher to consider potential strategies to support public school teachers in addressing challenges impacting their professional dedication and overall well-being. Gaining a comprehensive understanding of the complex relationship between mental health and teacher commitment carries substantial implications for initiatives related to educational policy, teacher welfare, and school improvement. These indicators motivated the researcher to conduct this study in order to assess the level of teacher commitment and the mental health of public school teachers in the Matina District, Davao City Division.

Specifically, the objectives of the study are

as follows: a) to determine the level of teacher commitment in terms of commitment to school, commitment to students, commitment to teaching, and commitment to profession; b) to the level of mental health in terms of lifestyle habits, work satisfaction, social relations, and financial struggles; and c) to determine which quantitative results on mental health experience require further explanation to identify what school program can be initiated to boost mental health and improve teacher commitment among public school teachers in the Matina District, Davao City Division.

The findings of this study have significantly contributed to various stakeholders. For the Department of Education, the research supported the development of early intervention programs and targeted policies to improve teachers' mental health, ensure high work satisfaction, and provide equal access to mental health services. Teachers benefited through institutional recommendations for programs, seminars, and activities that enhance their mental well-being and professional commitment, leading to greater job satisfaction, reduced burnout, and improved retention. Learners ultimately gained from having teachers with strong commitment and sound mental health, fostering a more supportive and effective learning environment. Lastly, the study serves as a valuable reference for future researchers interested in exploring the relationship between teacher commitment and mental health.

The conceptual framework of this study was structured around two key components: the mental health of teachers and their level of teacher commitment. Teachers' mental health was examined in terms of four specific dimensions: lifestyle habits, work satisfaction, social relations, and financial struggles. On the other hand, teacher commitment was explored through their commitment to school, commitment to students, commitment to teaching, and commitment to the profession. This framework

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

guided the investigation in determining the level of both mental health and teacher commitment among public school teachers in the Matina District, Davao City Division, as a basis for proposing a school program to boost mental wellness and strengthen professional commitment.

2. Methodology

This section presents the methodology components used in the study, such as the research design, ethical considerations, research respondents/participants, research instrument, data gathering procedure, data analysis and sequence, emphasis, and procedures.

2.1. Research Design—This study utilized an explanatory sequential mixed-method design to explore teacher commitment amidst mental health experiences. It began with a quantitative phase using survey questionnaires to gather data, followed by a qualitative phase involving interviews to explain the quantitative results further. Based on Creswell (2023), the rationale for this approach was to gain a general understanding through statistical analysis and then deepen that understanding by exploring teachers’ views and experiences. The qualitative data refined and elaborated on the quantitative findings, particularly in identifying which results required further explanation regarding teachers’ mental health and commitment.

2.2. Ethical Considerations—The researcher followed RMC’s ethical principles, ensuring the study had social value, upheld informed consent, minimized risks, protected privacy, and promoted fairness, transparency, and community involvement. The study aimed to benefit teachers, school heads, and students by examining how mental health affects teacher commitment. Participation was voluntary, with

respondents fully informed and allowed to withdraw at any time. Risks were minimal, and data were kept confidential per the Data Privacy Act 2012. The researcher was qualified, sought guidance when needed, used available facilities, and engaged the school community by sharing the study’s purpose and findings.

2.3. Research Respondents—This explanatory sequential mixed-method study aimed to determine teachers’ mental health experience and teaching commitment by first gathering quantitative data through a survey of 82 randomly selected public school teachers using the formula by Tabachnick and Fidell (2007). Simple random sampling ensured equal chances for selection and reduced bias, focusing only on teachers from Matina Central Elementary School with at least two years of experience. The study did not consider teachers’ rank or performance ratings. For the qualitative phase, five teachers who met the same criteria were purposively selected from the survey group for in-depth interviews to gain deeper insights into their experiences.

2.4. Research Instrument—This study examined the relationship between teachers’ men-

tal health and their commitment to teaching at Matina Central Elementary School. The independent variable, mental health, was measured through lifestyle habits, work satisfaction, social relations, and financial struggles, while teacher commitment was assessed in terms of commitment to school, students, teaching, and profession. Quantitative data were collected using two adapted and validated questionnaires. The first, developed by Thien et al. (2020), measured teacher commitment with similar items. Based on Zhang (2022), the second measure of mental health experiences included five items for each indicator. Both tools underwent expert validation and pilot testing. In the qualitative phase, a researcher-made interview guide was used to explore potential school programs to improve teacher mental health and commitment, with validation from five experts. Audio recordings from the interviews were reviewed for accuracy to ensure reliable data and findings.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—In this study, the researcher followed a systematic approach for both quantitative and qualitative data collection. Permission was sought from relevant authorities before administering surveys and conducting interviews. The questionnaires

underwent content validation by experts and were pilot-tested for reliability. Surveys were distributed face-to-face, ensuring rapport with respondents, and were analyzed using SPSS. The interview guide was validated for the qualitative phase, and in-depth interviews were conducted in a comfortable, confidential setting, with participants' consent to record the conversations. Thematic content analysis, supported by triangulation, was used to analyze the qualitative data, ensuring robust and reliable findings.

2.6. Data Analysis—To address the research questions, the study utilized the mean to assess the level of teachers' mental health experience and teacher commitment. Thematic Content Analysis (TCA) was employed for the qualitative data, following the six steps outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006). The process began with familiarizing the researcher with the data and generating initial codes to identify meaningful features. These codes were organized into themes, which were reviewed and refined to ensure coherence. The themes were then defined and named to capture their essence, and the final report was produced to present the analysis, supported by empirical evidence, addressing the research questions effectively.

3. Results and Discussion

This section highlights the study's results and discussion. The presentation starts with a descriptive analysis of teacher commitment and mental health and ends with a discussion of the themes to determine what school program can be initiated to boost work satisfaction and improve teacher commitment amidst mental health experiences.

3.1. Level of teacher commitment—Table 1 shows the level of teacher commitment, which was measured by four indicators, namely: (1) commitment to school, (2) commitment to students, (3) commitment to teaching, and (4) commitment to the profession. The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: Commitment to school (3.01) and commitment to students (2.95) are both rated as moderate, suggesting a bal-

anced level of dedication in these areas. Commitment to the profession (3.21) is also rated as moderate, reflecting a solid commitment to the field. However, commitment to teaching (2.57) is lower and categorized as low, indicating that teachers may experience challenges or dissatisfaction in this aspect. The overall mean score of 2.94 falls within the moderate range, indicating that while teachers are generally committed

to their roles and students, there is room for improvement, particularly in the area of teaching commitment. The average rating for this domain is 2.94, which is considered Moderate. This means that the level of teacher commitment is sometimes evident.

Table 1. Level of Teacher Commitment

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Commitment to School	3.01	Moderate
2	Commitment to Students	2.95	Moderate
3	Commitment to Teaching	2.57	Low
4	Commitment to Profession	3.21	Moderate
Overall		2.94	Moderate

Note. Legend: 1.00–1.79 = Very Low, 1.80–2.59 = Low, 2.60–3.39 = Moderate, 3.40–4.19 = High, 4.20–5.00 = Very High.

3.2. *Level of Teacher’s Mental Health*— Table 2 shows the level of teachers’ mental health experience, which was measured by four indicators, namely: (1) lifestyle habits, (2) work satisfaction, (3) social relations, and (4) financial struggles. The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: The mean scores for lifestyle habits (3.18) and social relations (3.14) fall under the moderate category, suggesting a moderate impact on mental health in these areas. However, work satisfaction (2.59) and financial struggles (2.73) are rated lower, with both indicators falling into the low to moderate range, highlighting areas where teachers may experience challenges affecting their mental well-being. The overall mean score of 2.91 also reflects a moderate level of mental health experience, suggesting that while there are some positive aspects, notable concerns in work-related and financial areas could impact teachers’ overall mental health. The overall mean rating on this domain was marked as Moderate (2.91). This means that the level of mental health of teachers is sometimes evident.

Table 2. Level of Teacher’s Mental Health Experience

No.	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Lifestyle habits	3.18	Moderate
2	Work satisfaction	2.59	Low
3	Social relations	3.14	Moderate
4	Financial struggles	2.73	Moderate
Overall		2.91	Moderate

Note. Legend: 1.00–1.79 = Very Low, 1.80–2.59 = Low, 2.60–3.39 = Moderate, 3.40–4.19 = High, 4.20–5.00 = Very High.

Fig. 2. School Program

3.3. *The school program was initiated to boost work satisfaction and improve teacher commitment amidst mental health experiences*—Figure 2 shows the school program initiated to boost work satisfaction and improve teacher commitment amidst mental health experiences. Three (3) themes were found, namely: (1) Recognizing and rewarding, (2) Positive working conditions, and (3) Increasing opportunities for growth. The results showed that the participants’ responses were based on their experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights from the presented variables.

The first theme identified to boost work satisfaction and improve teacher commitment amidst mental health experiences was recognition and reward. Organizational recognition and reward systems aim to increase extrinsic moti-

vation by satisfying employees’ desires through pay and incentives, which enhances satisfaction, performance, and commitment. The second theme is the promotion of positive working conditions, which encompass factors that support employee safety, growth, and goal attainment. A positive working environment motivates teachers to perform to their best abilities, leading to greater satisfaction and commitment to their roles. Lastly, the theme of increasing opportunities for growth highlights the importance of employee training and development programs. These initiatives allow teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills, fostering greater job satisfaction and, in turn, improving their commitment to teaching. Together, these themes contribute to boosting teacher work satisfaction and commitment, despite mental health challenges.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study aimed to determine the level of teacher commitment, which was measured by four indicators, namely: (1) commitment to school, (2) commitment to students, (3) commitment to teaching, and (4) commitment to the profession. And to determine the level of teacher’s mental health experience which is measured by four indicators namely: (1) lifestyle habits, (2) work satisfaction, (3) social relation, and (4) financial struggles, Additionally, the study dug deeper to determine what quantitative results further explanation to determine what school program can be initiated to boost work satisfaction of teachers in improving teaching commitment amidst mental health experience of public school teachers teaching in Matina Central Elementary School, Matina District, Davao City Division for the school year 2023-2024. The following are the significant findings:

4.1. *Findings*—The level of teacher commitment, in terms of commitment to school, was sometimes evident. The level of teacher commitment, in terms of commitment to students, was sometimes evident. The level of teacher commitment, in terms of commitment to

teaching, was seldom evident. And the level of teacher commitment, in terms of commitment to the profession, was sometimes evident. Overall, the teacher commitment garnered a mean score equivalent to moderate, which also means that the commitment of the teachers was sometimes

evident.

The level of teacher mental health regarding lifestyle habits was sometimes evident. The level of teacher mental health experience regarding work satisfaction was seldom evident. The level of teacher mental health experience in terms of social relations was sometimes evident. And the level of teacher mental health experience in terms of financial struggles was sometimes evident. Overall, teachers' mental health level garnered a mean score equivalent to moderate, which also means that it was sometimes evident.

For the qualitative data, three themes emerged after the thematic content analysis. School programs that boost teachers' work satisfaction and improve teaching commitment amidst mental health experience are: (1) recognizing and rewarding their effort, and rewarding them based on their performance. (2) positive working conditions, by fostering an environment which are not only conducive for learning but also for teachers to improve their commitment to teaching, and (3) increasing opportunities for growth, to learn and increase their

knowledge in their profession.

4.2. *Recommendations*—Based on the findings, it is recommended that the Department of Education implement early intervention programs to support teachers facing mental health challenges and use the findings to develop targeted policies and programs that promote high work satisfaction and ensure equal access to mental health services for all educators. Additionally, school institutions should be encouraged to enhance teachers' mental health experiences and commitment through tailored programs, seminars, and activities, addressing their needs to reduce burnout and improve retention. Ultimately, students would benefit from a more secure and conducive learning environment created by teachers who are mentally and emotionally healthy, as such teachers are better equipped to engage students and provide quality instruction. Finally, this study serves as a resource for future research, encouraging further exploration into additional factors influencing teachers' mental health and commitment, using diverse methodologies and variables not addressed in this research.

5. References

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